

Perceived Value in Green Products: A Bibliometric Review Using R Studio and VOS Viewer

Anju Maria Baby T.*¹, Leena Varghese²

¹Research Scholar, Al-Ameen College, Edathala. Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, St. Kuriakose College of Management and Science, Kuruppampady

²Associate Professor & Research Supervisor, Al Ameen College, Edathala

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine how perceived value is conceptualised and integrated into green products and sustainable consumption studies. 134 articles from the Scopus database were used for the study. Data were retrieved on 31st January 2026 and selected according to the PRISMA guidelines. The study was conducted using RStudio and VOS viewer. The findings showed an increasing pattern in the number of publications. Sustainability (Switzerland) is the most productive journal. Yadav R, 2017, has received 1027 citations for the document "Determinants of consumers' green purchasing behaviour in a developing Nation: Applying and extending the Theory of Planned Behaviour, and is considered the most cited document. India is the most cited country with 1248 citations. China is the most productive country. Perceived value is a frequently used keyword. Environmental awareness, decision making, and green consumption are the least explored themes. The findings have significant implications for scholars, marketers, and consumers since they provide insight into research patterns, publication and citation status.

Keywords: Perceived value, Green products, PRISMA, R Studio, Biblioshiny, VOS viewer

INTRODUCTION

Green products play a significant role in economic and sustainable development. Growing environmental concerns are shifting consumer behaviour towards green products with organic ingredients, cruelty-free testing and sustainable packaging (Handriana et al., 2025). Consumers are more conscious about their health, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic. To protect themselves and their family consumers' demand for green products has been increasing. Increased concerns about global environmental issues have led to a growing focus on environmentally conscious consumption and a shift away from traditional habits (Hoang & Tung, 2024). Responsible consumption is necessary for the well-being of society. In recent years awareness of the environmental issue has been raised and popularized globally (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023). Healthy ecosystems are gaining the pivotal role in the world due to strong effects on well being & health (Ahmed et al., 2020). Human consumption is regarded as one of the main sources responsible for climate change,

depletion of scarce resources (Ahmed et al., 2020). The rapid environmental changes have developed serious threats to many business organization (Qureshi et al., 2023). They are more willing to protect the environment as part of their social responsibility (Qureshi et al., 2023). Increasing global awareness of environmental issues and demand for eco-friendly products have spurred organisations to develop green marketing strategies (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023). So besides the Government regulations demand for green products has led to the development of the ecological product industry (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023). Marketers considered green consumption as a good opportunity to meet changing customer demand (Chaudhary, 2018). So, many firms are producing eco-friendly products to attract the eco-conscious buyers. The responsible production and consumption (SDG 12) play a pivotal role in sustainable development, its main objective is to prevent harmful effects on health and environment, reducing waste and living in a way that is good for environment (Rustagi et al., n.d.). Many firms have been developing their marketing strategies in order to

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

adapt to the needs of customers and to follow the trend (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023). Sustainable consumption, particularly the usage of green products gaining importance as it minimises environmental impact through resource conservation and pollution reduction (Ahmed et al., 2020). While opting for green products, consumers evaluate the benefits they receive compared to the cost they pay. Consumers are willing to pay more (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023).for products that give more value to them. Many studies say that perceived value (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023) (Ahmed et al., 2020) (Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023) (Shih et al., 2024) (Handriana et al., 2025) (Rustagi et al., n.d.) (Hoang & Tung, 2024) (Román-Augusto et al., 2022) (Filip et al., 2025) and purchase intention are positively related. The higher the perceived value, the stronger the intention to purchase. Perceived value has positive influence on repurchase intention of green agricultural products (Xu et al., 2022). Perceived value is a core construct in marketing, defined as a consumer's subjective evaluation of a product's worth based on comparing benefits to costs (Yang et al., 2024) (Chen et al., 2021) (Chi et al., 2021) (Román-Augusto et al., 2022) (Tsai et al., 2025). Perceived value act as a mediator in the relationship between perceived sustainability and customer satisfaction by translating the sustainability efforts into emotional and social benefits (Shih et al., 2024) . When consumers become more aware about the value of purchasing sustainable goods, they prioritize making eco-friendly choices (Ilagan et al., 2024). Consumers tend to perceive value based on their past experiences, and this value is categorized into various aspects (Kim & Kim, 2025). The theory of consumption value suggests that consumption is influenced by multiple independent values that contribute differently to choice (Yang et al., 2024) . Green buying behaviour involves consumer choices of eco-friendly products that contribute to environmental preservation, with perceived value playing a significant role in these decisions (Handriana et al., 2025). This study aims to examine how perceived value is conceptualised and integrated into the green products and sustainable consumption research. It contributes to the existing literature through a bibliometric analysis. The following are the research questions:

RQ1: What is the annual pattern of publications on perceived value in green products consumer behaviour research?

RQ2: Who are the most influential authors, articles and journals contributing to perceived value research in green product consumption?

RQ3: Which are the most cited countries in perceived value and green consumption research? RQ4: Which countries and affiliations are the most productive in this field?

RQ5: What are the most frequently used keywords in perceived value and green product consumer behaviour research?

RQ6: What are the main research themes integrating perceived value and green product consumption behaviour?

RQ7: What are the collaboration patterns among countries in this field?

The study focuses on consumer behaviour regarding green products by addressing the aforementioned questions. Despite many bibliometric analyses have examined green buying behaviour, limited attention has been paid to how perceived value has been conceptualised and integrated into green products consumer behaviour research. This study aims to bridge the gap to identify publication patterns, top publishing journals, the top producing authors, keywords, and thematic evolution of perceived value in green consumption.

METHODOLOGY

The present study employs bibliometric analysis to investigate research trends related to the perceived value of green products and sustainable consumption. Bibliometric analysis finds the current worldwide research trends in a particular field. It analyses and evaluate vast volume of scientific data. A bibliometric examination of the academic literature on perceived value in sustainable consumption served as the foundation for the technique used in the present research. It is a quantitative research method that systematically analyse academic publications. This study aims to understand how research in this area has developed. Three steps make up the structure of the

study: 1. Data Collection 2. Bibliometric analysis and information visualisation 3. Presenting and summarizing the findings.

Data Collection

The data was collected from the Scopus database, which is one of the largest database and has a wide coverage of journals, conference papers and research articles in various discipline especially in the field of business, management and social science. Data was retrieved on 31st January 2026. The following research string was used to search the data:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("green product*" OR "sustainable product*" OR "eco-friendly product*")

OR "green consumption" OR "sustainable consumption" AND "consumer behaviour" OR "consumer behavior" OR "purchase intention" AND "perceived value" OR "value adoption model" OR "VAM")

Only research articles, conference papers, book chapters were selected. The time period from 2000 – 2026 was considered. Only articles published in English were included; other

language excluded. Studies related to consumer behaviour and perceived value in green products were

focused. Initially, 189 articles were identified. After applying the inclusion criteria 134 articles were selected for the final analysis.

Bibliometric analysis

Performance analysis and scientific mapping are the two important bibliometric trends used in this study. Performance analysis was done to quantify the literature’s production in terms of publications by nation, author, affiliated institution and time period. Scientific mapping aims to identify theme developments and intellectual structures in the topic of study. This analysis quantitatively measure the productivity of research output. The present scenario and growth may be updated with the help of this analysis. The selected data was analysed using 2 software: R Studio and VOS viewer. R studio is a statistical software used for data analysis. Using bibliometrix, the study analysed: annual scientific production, most relevant authors, most cited documents, most collaborative nations, productive countries and institutions, keyword frequency, thematic analysis. VOSviewer was used to visualize bibliometric networks. It is widely used in academic research for mapping relationships. In this study VOS was usednfor keyword co-occurrence analysis.

Table 1 Overview of the key research

Sr. No	Authors	Period of the study	Objectives	Findings
1	(Shih et al., 2024)	2024	How perceived value mediates the relationship between sustainability and customer satisfaction	Sustainability perceptions influence perceived value, which in turn affects customer satisfaction.
2	(Nguyen Tran Cam, 2023)	2023	To test the relationship between green perceived value, green perceived risk, green trust and green purchase intention.	Green perceived value positively affect both Green trust and green purchase intention. Green perceived risk positively affect green trust but has no impact on purchase intention.
3	(Handriana et al., 2025)	2023	Analysed consumer behaviour toward environmentally friendly cosmetics.	Both utilitarian and hedonic values positively influence green product satisfaction
4	(Hudayah et al., 2023)	2023	To examine how Gen z consumers views on the value of green products, and also to know how their concern for the environment changes the input of these values.	Functional value and conditional value, along with environmental concern, boost green products' purchase intention. Social value impact on buying green products grows stronger with great environmental concern. The mix of

				social and environmental motivations shapes Gen z sustainable habits.
5	(Yang et al., 2024)	2022	How perceived value influence consumer attitude and purchase intention towards sustainable luxury products	Social value affects attitude and purchase intention, hedonic value had a positive link with attitude and insignificant with purchase intention.
6	(Abubakari et al., 2025)	2025	Explore the relationship between trust, perceived value and premium price.	Green perceived value mediates the relationship between green products experiences and willingness to pay more. Trust indirectly influences willingness to pay through perceived value.
7	(Nassanbekova et al., 2024)	2024	To examine what factors influence young consumers in Kazakhstan to buy green products by extending Theory of planned Behaviour with perceived value and environmental knowledge.	Environmental knowledge and emotional value are the strongest predictors of green purchase intention, social value has weak influence.
8	(Hoo et al., 2025)	2025	Factors affecting adoption of green life styles, emphasizing brand credibility, loyalty, expertise, environmental awareness and value perception.	Environmental awareness and consumer value play a key role in driving eco-friendly behaviours. Building brand trust and making authentic Green claims encourage consumers to adopt sustainable practices.
9	(Suttikun et al., 2025)	2024	To examine how different types of green advertisement messages affect brand awareness, intention to share advertisements, and purchase intention at eco- friendly coffee retailers.	Ads showing clear benefits with supportive green images were most effective and the emotional value and functional value strongly increase purchase intention.
10	(Ngo et al., 2024)	2024	To investigate the factors influencing Gen z purchase intention toward sustainable clothing.	Perceived value, quality, price, social influence, product design, environmental concern and knowledge positively affect attitude, and affects purchase intention.

Source: Authors Compilation

Data Source

The literature was searched electronically using Scopus database. It was chosen because they contain vast amount of information on scientific and

consumer behaviour research (Dwivedi et al., 2025). Data was retrieved on 31st January 2026, served as the data source for this investigation. It is a comprehensive database that indexes scholarly literature, including academic journals, conference proceedings and books. The steps for recovering the article and further analysis are shown in Figure 1

Source: Author compilation using PRISMA

In order to capture the recent research trend in sustainable consumption, the 2000-2026 period was chosen. A total of 189 articles were found during the first step. After utilising the Boolean operators “AND”, “OR”, “NOT” to search for documents and got 134 articles finally. All the information (abstract, authors, nations, year of publication, document kinds, source journal, title, subject categories and cited references) was included in the records exported. We constructed and visualized bibliometric network using the free bibliometric analysis VOS viewer (version 1.6.20), which is extensively used worldwide. Advanced bibliometric studies were conducted using the Bibliometrix package and its integrated online interface, Biblioshiny (for R Studio version 2025.5.1), in addition to the VOS viewer.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Key Information

According to figure 1, 396 authors published 134 articles in 77 journals between 2000 and 2026. The studies include 1080 references with an average of 35.92 citations per document. There are 127 documents with multiple authors, but only 7 documents have a single author. International collaboration appears in 29.1% of the publications, with an average of 3.31 co-authors per document. The average age of the documents, 3.25 years, it shows that research has only recently increased. It is quite interesting that the 451 author-supplied keywords are in this data set. With an annual growth rate of 14.78 per cent, the number of publications has increased in the past year. This shows the importance of

sustainability and green consumer behaviour in academic research. Important descriptive statistics

and high-level details about the bibliometric dataset are provided by this bibliometric profile.

Figure 2 Data base information

Source: Biblioshiny

Performance Analysis

This section was conducted using R Studio to evaluate the scientific productivity and impact within the area of perceived value in green consumption. Using bibliometrix package, key indicators such as annual scientific production, most relevant authors, top authors, authors production through Lotka’s law, most cited document, were examined

❖ **Annual Scientific Production**

The total number of publications in the field determines the annual development rate of scientific production. The evolution of publications on sustainable behaviour that are accessible through the Scopus database between 2000 and 2026 is shown in Table 2. A total of 134 documents have been found. The publication of research articles has increased. A strong increase in the post-pandemic era (2020-2026), but shows a slight decline in 2023; it can be considered a short-term fluctuation, not a lack of research interest, because we see a sharp increase in 2024 and 2025. With 43 articles published, 2025 was the year with the most articles.

Table 2: Annual Scientific Production

Year	Articles
2013	1
2014	2
2015	3
2016	1
2017	6
2018	1
2019	3
2020	8
2021	4
2022	18
2023	13
2024	25
2025	43
2026	6

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Most Relevant Authors**

Each author's scientific production is calculated on the basis of the number of papers they have contributed. According to the number of papers published,

Dangelico R, Fraccascia L was the most productive author with 4 papers, as shown in figure 2. Annamdevulla S, Bozdog L-Ş, Sinha R, Wang J were among the authors who contributed 3 articles between

2017 and 2025. From 2023-2026, Abubakari A, Amoako G K, Ampong Goa, Baljir K each contributed 2 articles.

Figure 3: Most Relevant Authors

Source: Biblioshiny

Table 3: Production list of the Top Authors (Top articles and Citations)

Author	year	freq	TC	TCpY
Abubakari A	2023	1	17	4.25
Abubakari A	2025	1	2	1
Amoako Gk	2023	1	17	4.25
Amoako Gk	2025	1	2	1
Ampong Goa	2023	1	17	4.25
Ampong Goa	2025	1	2	1
Annamdevula S	2023	1	11	2.75
Annamdevula S	2025	2	12	6
Baljir K	2024	1	7	2.333
Baljir K	2026	1	0	0
Bozdog L-Ş	2025	3	2	1
Dangelico R	2022	1	110	22
Dangelico R	2024	2	42	14
Dangelico R	2025	1	0	0
Fraccascia L	2022	1	110	22
Fraccascia L	2024	2	42	14
Fraccascia L	2025	1	0	0
Sinha R	2023	1	11	2.75
Sinha R	2025	2	12	6
Wang J	2017	1	75	7.5
Wang J	2023	1	35	8.75
Wang J	2025	1	0	0

Source: Biblioshiny

The study adopted Lotka’s law, which plots the number of authors on a logarithmic scale against the

number of contributions they made. According to Lotka’s law, 89.9% of the researchers generated only one document. Figure 4 shows the percentage of authors who have contributed 2 papers: 8.6%

generated 2 papers, 1% generated 3 papers, 0.5% generated 4 papers. According to Table 4 majority of the authors published 1 article, the highest number of articles is 4.

Figure 4: Frequency distribution of scientific productivity

Source: Biblioshiny

Table 4 Author's Production through Lotka's law

Documents written	N. of Authors	Proportion of Authors
1	357	0.899
2	34	0.086
3	4	0.01
4	2	0.005

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Most Cited Document**

According to a review of the most widely cited documents, Figure 5 shows that Yadav R, 2017, (Ecological Economics) whose paper “Determinants of consumers green purchase behaviour in a

developing Nation: Applying & Extending the theory of planned behaviour” received 1029 citations, was the most productive author. Park HJ, 2020 received 608 citations. 357 citations for Roh T (2022), 244 for Ammad W (2020), 178 for DeMedeiros (2016), 131 for Jeang Y (2015), 110 for Dangellico R (2022), 103 for Wagner M M(2020), 88 for Cheung R (2015), 85 for Chen L (2021).

Figure 5: Most cited Document

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Most Productive Journal Sources**

The top ten journals with the most contributions to perceived value and consumer behaviour towards green products are shown in Figure 6. A total of 77 journals have been located. Sustainability (Switzerland) was the most productive journal source

with 23 articles published. Journal of Cleaner Production published 8 articles. Business Strategy and the Environment published 5 articles. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services published 4 articles. Acta Psychologica, Behavioural Sciences, environment and social psychology, International Journal of Sustainable Development, PLOS ONE, Society and Business Review published 3 articles each.

Figure 6: Most Productive Journal Sources

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Most Cited Countries**

With 1248 citations, India is the most highlighted nation in sustainable consumption studies, based on

Figure 7. With 1030 citations, Korea stands in second, followed by China (882). Brazil, USA, Italy, Hongkong, Peru, UK, Australia receive 281,207,198,133,117,103,88 citations respectively.

Figure 7: Most Cited Countries

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Most productive countries**

National scientific production helps to identify the geographic areas of resource concentration, with 70 articles China leads the world in geographical productivity by country followed by the India (27),

Korea (18), Malaysia (18), Italy (17), Indonesia (11), and other countries have produced below 10 articles.

Figure 8: Countries Scientific Production

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Most productive affiliations**

Chadyang University of Technology, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University has published the maximum number of articles with 6, followed by Sapienza

Università di Roma with 5 publications. FPT University, Ghana communication technology university, Mapua University, Politecnico Di Bari, and Universiteit Twente has published 4 articles. Chung shan medical university, chung shan medical university hospital has published 3 articles.

Figure 9: Most productive affiliations

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ **Science Mapping**

It focuses on the connections between every aspect of research. The study focuses on the structured

relationships and intellectual exchanges between all of the elements of the research. Citation analysis, co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, co-word analysis and co-authorship analysis are some of the methods used in scientific mapping.

Figure 10: Keyword co-occurrence

Source: VOS viewer

❖ **Top ten author keywords**

Table 5: Top ten author keywords

Keywords	Occurences
Perceived value	43
Purchase intention	26
Consumer behaviour	23
Consumption behaviour	23
Green perceived value	23
Perception	22
Sustainability	21
Sustainable consumption	21
Green purchase intention	20
Green products	16

Source: Biblioshiny

Word Cloud Mapping

In word clouds, the most prevalent words are at the centre, surrounded by less common alternatives as

indicated by the keywords width in Figure 10. The outcomes of the word cloud show that perceived value, purchase intention, consumption behaviour, consumer behaviour, green perceived value were the most commonly used topics.

Figure 11: Word cloud

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ Thematic Analysis

A thematic map in bibliometric analysis illustrates a topics conceptual structure. The co-occurrence network shows clusters and keywords. Centrality on the x-axis denotes how prominent a theme is on the map. Higher centrality themes are more significant in the network and have more connections. Density represented by the Y-axis, illustrates how themes are related to one another and how developed they are. Following are the 4 quadrants of thematic map:

- **Motor Theme:** The motor theme, which is located in the upper right quadrant, represents important and well-developed themes that influence the research area. The motor or driving themes are consumer behaviour, attitude and human.
- **Basic Theme:** Basic themes concentrating on broad subjects across multiple research domains are identified in the lower right quadrant. It represents consumption behaviour, green perceived value, perception, perceived value, purchase intention, green products. These are the key themes in green marketing.
- **Niche Theme:** Niche themes, which have undergone substantial development but have little significance, are shown by the upper left quadrant. This area contains themes like sustainable products, consumer psychology, emotional value, sustainable consumption, consumer psychology, emotional value, sustainable consumption, sustainable development, and willingness to pay.
- **Emerging or declining themes:** These are represented by the lower left quadrant, which denotes areas that require more research and development. It includes green consumption, environmental awareness, and decision making.

Figure 12: Thematic Map Analysis

Source: Biblioshiny

❖ Collaboration Network Countries

Figure 12 illustrates each Nation's international co-operation. Countries that are published is displayed in blue and the countries that have no publication yet is

displayed in grey. The red light shows the collaboration network, thickness of the line shows its strength of collaboration. From the analysis it shows that China is the most productive country and it has highest number of publication. India, Hong Kong, Ghana, France, Australia and other nations involved in the partnership.

Figure 13: Most Collaborative Countries

Source: Biblioshiny

FUTURE RESEARCH

Future research should focus on actual green purchase behaviour. Most of the studies end with purchase intention, but it is important to examine the real behaviour in order to identify the attitude-intention gap. Greenwashing is another important issue, that is less explored. So, the future studies should investigate whether the greenwashing moderates value and intention. The growing influence of social media platform and AI recommendations should be addressed, as these are the most relevant issues in the present digital environment.

DISCUSSION

The study uses bibliometric analysis of 134 academic papers from Scopus to understand the intellectual framework in the area of perceived value in green product consumption. Through performance analysis, the study examined annual scientific production, the most productive authors, the most cited articles, and productive countries. Additionally, areas, authors, topics, document, countries and institutions are linked together as shown by the science mapping studies. The studies showed an increasing pattern in the number of publications in this field (RQ1). The growth in publications, particularly after 2020, shows the global awareness of sustainability, the influence of SDG's. It indicate a shift in consumer priorities toward health and environment responsibility. Yadav

R, 2017, (Ecological Economics)- "Determinants of consumers' green purchase behaviour in a developing Nation: Applying and extending the Theory of Planned Behaviour" received 1027 citations, is the most cited document (RQ2). Sustainability (Switzerland), which published 23 articles, is the most productive journal (RQ2). India is the most cited country with 1248 citations (RQ3). China is the most productive country (70 articles), Changyang University of Technology, and Hangkong Polytechnic University are the most productive affiliations. Another key finding of this study is the central role of perceived value in green consumption research. Perceived value is the most frequently used keyword, followed by purchase intention, consumer behaviour, and consumption behaviour. It shows that perceived value act as a mediator in translating environmental attributes into behavioural intentions. The thematic analysis of consumer behaviour, attitude and human are the motor themes, whereas consumption behaviour, green perceived value, perception, perceived value, purchase intention and green products are the key themes in marketing. The least explored themes are environmental awareness, decision making, and green consumption. All the above findings have significant implications for scholars, marketers, and consumers since they provide insight into research patterns, publication and citation status. The study will help to concentrate on the most productive journal and most cited papers in order to gather valuable and practical knowledge.

CONCLUSION

The present study examines the role of perceived value in green product consumption through a bibliometric analysis. The data was retrieved from the Scopus database for the time period of 2000-2026. 134 articles were used for the study. The findings show that there is a steady growth in research related to the green consumption, in recent years. This reflects the rapid increase in sustainability & environmentally responsible behaviour. Perceived value is a central concept in green consumption research. Keywords such as perceived value, consumer behaviour, Purchase intention dominate the research field. It shows the growing importance in understanding sustainable consumption patterns. China is the most productive country and India is the most cited country. From thematic analysis it reveals that environmental awareness and decision making are emerging. Overall this study provides a comprehensive overview of the intellectual structure and development of perceived value in green product research. It provides valuable insights for researchers, marketers and policymakers to understand trends and promote sustainable consumption behaviour.

IMPLICATIONS

This study contributes to the existing literature. Perceived value is the key factor in sustainable consumption research. It is a multidimensional concept including Functional value, Emotional value, Social value, Cultural value, Epistemic value. It provides a deeper understanding of how consumers evaluate green products. In addition, environmental awareness and decision making serve as directions for future academic research. This study helps scholars to identify gaps and develop more theoretical models. The study also provides implications for marketers and business organization. Companies should focus on perceived value of green products, because consumers should understand the value they receive. Government can promote green consumption by creating awareness programmes and encouraging sustainable life styles.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is based on data collected from Scopus database. Future research can include other databases

for more comprehensive analysis. The present study considered only articles in English language. This may exclude any important article from other language. Bibliometric analysis shows only the quantitative evaluation doesn't provide any in-depth qualitative insights. So, future studies should include SLR, by combining bibliometric analysis with SLR to gain a deeper understanding.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

Not applicable Conflict of interest:

Regarding the research, writing, and or publishing of this paper, the authors have declared that they have no conflicts of interest.

Funding:

The authors did not receive any financial support for this research.

REFERENCE

1. Ahmed, M. A., Arshad, A., Anwar Ul Haq, M., & Akram, B. (2020). Role of Environmentalism in the Development of Green Purchase Intentions: A Moderating Role of Green Product Knowledge. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, 15(7), 1101–1111. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijstdp.150714>
2. Chaudhary, R. (2018). Green buying behavior in India: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 9(2), 179–192. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-12-2017-0058>
3. Chen, L., Qie, K., Memon, H., & Yesuf, H. M. (2021). The Empirical Analysis of Green Innovation for Fashion Brands, Perceived Value and Green Purchase Intention—Mediating and Moderating Effects. *Sustainability*, 13(8), 4238. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084238>
4. Chi, T., Ganak, J., Summers, L., Adesanya, O., McCoy, L., Liu, H., & Tai, Y. (2021). Understanding Perceived Value and Purchase Intention toward Eco-Friendly Athleisure Apparel: Insights from U.S. Millennials. *Sustainability*, 13(14), 7946. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147946>
5. Dwivedi, S., Gupta, A., & Sayal, A. (2025). Evolution of consumer perceptions and intentions in the green cosmetics market: A thematic and

- trend analysis. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 6, 1617779.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2025.1617779>
6. Filip, A., Stancu, A., Onișor, L.-F., Mogoș, O. C., Catană, Ștefan-A., & Goldbach, D. (2025). Drivers of Purchase Intentions of Generation Z on Eco-Products. *Sustainability*, 17(2), 629. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17020629>
 7. Handriana, T., Usman, I., Sangadji, S. S., & Mehta, A. M. (2025). The Environmentally Friendly Cosmetics: Perceived Values, Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty Aspects. *Malaysian Journal of Consumer and Family Economics*, 34(1), 298–326. <https://doi.org/10.60016/majcafe.v34.10>
 8. Hoang, D., & Tung, L. (2024). Effect of Environmental concern, Green perceived value on Young customers' green purchase intention: The mediating roles of Attitude toward green products and Perceived behavior control. *Scientific Papers of the University of Pardubice, Series D: Faculty of Economics and Administration*, 32(1). <https://doi.org/10.46585/sp32011920>
 9. Hudayah, S., Aulia Ramadhani, M., Arum Sary, K., Raharjo, S., & Yudaruddin, R. (2023). Green perceived value and green product purchase intention of Gen Z consumers: Moderating role of environmental concern. *Environmental Economics*, 14(2), 87–102. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ee.14\(2\).2023.07](https://doi.org/10.21511/ee.14(2).2023.07)
 10. Ilagan, S. M. C., Ong, A. K. S., German, J. D., Gumasing, Ma. J. J., & Pabalan, K. M. P. (2024). Holistic Antecedent Analysis of Behavioral Intention among Green Consumers in the Philippines: A Sustainability Theory of the Planned Behavior Approach. *Sustainability*, 16(10), 3894. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16103894>
 11. Kim, B., & Kim, D. (2025). Understanding the Drivers of Sustainable Consumption in China: Role of Green Self-Identity, Subjective Norm, and Demographics. *Sage Open*, 15(4), 21582440251390627. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440251390627>
 12. Nassanbekova, S., Yeshekulova, G., Nurguzhina, A., & Ibadildin, N. (2024). Green Product Purchase Intention of Young Customers from Developing Country: Extended Theory of Planned Behavior. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, 19(9), 3633–3642. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijstdp.190931>
 13. Nguyen Tran Cam, L. (2023). A rising trend in eco-friendly products: A health-conscious approach to green buying. *Heliyon*, 9(9), e19845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19845>
 14. Qureshi, M. A., Khaskheli, A., Qureshi, J. A., Raza, S. A., & Khan, K. A. (2023). Factors influencing green purchase behavior among millennials: The moderating role of religious values. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 14(6), 1417–1437. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-06-2020-0174>
 15. Román-Augusto, J. A., Garrido-Lecca-Vera, C., Lodeiros-Zubiria, M. L., & Mauricio- Andia, M. (2022a). Green Marketing: Drivers in the Process of Buying Green Products—The Role of Green Satisfaction, Green Trust, Green WOM and Green Perceived Value. *Sustainability*, 14(17), 10580. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710580>
 16. Román-Augusto, J. A., Garrido-Lecca-Vera, C., Lodeiros-Zubiria, M. L., & Mauricio- Andia, M. (2022b). Green Marketing: Drivers in the Process of Buying Green Products—The Role of Green Satisfaction, Green Trust, Green WOM and Green Perceived Value. *Sustainability*, 14(17), 10580. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710580>
 17. Rustagi, P., Prakash, C., & Yadav, K. (n.d.). Environment Attitude, Long Term Health Orientation in Predicting Green Food Purchase Intention Among GEN Z.
 18. Suttikun, C., Mahasuweerachai, P., & Bicksler, W. H. (2025). Environmental messaging, corporate values, online engagement and purchase behavior: A study of green communications among eco-friendly coffee retailers. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 8(3), 1073–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-06-2024-0556>
 19. Tsai, C.-M., Kao, W.-Y., & Liu, W.-C. (2025). Navigating Sustainable Mobility in Taiwan: Exploring the Brand-Specific Effects of Perceived Green Attributes on the Green Purchase Intention for Battery Electric Vehicles. *Sustainability*, 17(3), 985. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17030985>

20. Xu, A., Wei, C., Zheng, M., Sun, L., & Tang, D. (2022). Influence of Perceived Value on Repurchase Intention of Green Agricultural Products: From the Perspective of Multi-Group Analysis. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 15451. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215451>
21. Yang, H., Cheng, J., Schaefer, A. D., & Kojo, S. (2024). Influencing factors of Chinese consumers' purchase intention towards sustainable luxury. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 36(9), 2054–2067. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-03-2022-0198>
22. Shih, I.-T., Dayarana K. Silalahi, A., Baljir, K., & Shinetseseg Jargalsaikhan. (2024). Exploring the impact of perceived sustainability on customer satisfaction and the mediating role of perceived value. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 2431647. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2431647>
23. Abubakari, A., Majeed, M., Amoako, G. K., Ofori, K. S., & Ampong, G. O. A. (2025). Going green, paying more: The relationship between trust in green labeling, green perceived value and price premiums. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 17(3), 381–404. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQSS-09-2023-0132>
24. Ngo, T. T. A., Vo, C. H., Tran, N. L., Nguyen, K. V., Tran, T. D., & Trinh, Y. N. (2024). Factors influencing Generation Z's intention to purchase sustainable clothing products in Vietnam. *PLOS ONE*, 19(12), e0315502. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0315502>
25. Hoo, W. C., Yang, Y. Q., Madhavedi, S., & Paraman, P. (2025). The influence of brand perceptions and consumer behavior on green lifestyle adoption in Malaysia: An empirical study. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, 20(8), 3171–3185. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijmdp.200802>.

HOW TO CITE: Anju Maria Baby T.*, Leena Varghese, Perceived Value in Green Products: A Bibliometric Review Using R Studio and VOS Viewer, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (4), 375-390. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19543967>